

Innochain Network Journal #3

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Contents

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FIG. FLECTOFOLD - AN ELASTIC-KINETIC MATERIAL-GRADIENT FACADE COMPONENT
BY SAMAN SAFFARIAN (ESR12)

Welcome to Innochain Network Journal #3 assembled and edited by KTH School of Architecture, Stockholm. Since Network Journal#2 that covered the 1st year Colloquium, Innochain has organized the Midterm Review events hosted by IAAC in Barcelona at the research centre and Self Sufficient Labs in Valdaura coupled with three parallel workshop-seminars, Workshop-seminar 2.1: Design Communication in Shared Virtual Space led by Damjan Minovski, Workshop-seminar 2.2: Simulation Fundamentals: The Lattice led by Pablo Miranda and Workshop-seminar 2.3: Materialising Design - Extending the Vocabulary of 3D Printing led by Alexandre Dubor and Raimund Krenmüller.

As Innochain now moved into the second half of its programme, we see how the ESRs are advancing their research, repositioning themselves in relation to the current use of digital design in building culture, investigating more integrative approaches to early stage design and enhancing interdisciplinary collaboration.

The Midterm Review provided an important opportunity for the Innochain network to focus the efforts of ESRs, Academic and

Industry Partners. The Workshop-seminars that were organized right after the Midterm Review at IAAC, supported the ESRs in formulating perspectives on their own research in dialogue with workshop leaders and colleagues.

We can now see how each ESR research promises concrete contributions to the field, and how they are right now furthering their collaborations with industry partners. We can see this, for example, in the development of demonstrators such as the FlectoFold large scale demonstrator, an elastic-kinetic material-gradient facade component system designed by Saman Saffarian (ESR12); Tom Svilans (ESR02) and industry partner Blumer Lehmann have developed techniques to integrate scanning and feedback technologies into glulam production and with White arkitektur in Stockholm has looked at how his research can inform emerging timber-based projects. Many of the ESRs are engaging in reassessing workflow between different expertise and different users, and exchange during the design process. Dimitrie Stefanescu (ESR05) in his research and development of the Speckle platform, challenges existing design communication standards such as BIM, and intends to improve the communication flows throughout the whole value chain. By developing different software tools to help expert users to get a better overview over large amounts of data, Paul Poinet (ESR06) is also looking at ways of improving this workflow. Zeynep Aksoz (ESR04) in her research is developing a design methodology that considers the possibility of engaging multiple criteria, assessing design performance of multiple variations at early design phase. She has recently been working with physical design artefacts, learning from physical feedback during a stay at IAAC where she conducted experiments with students on so called 'Zeer Pots'.

Wood as a dynamically active material on an architectural scale is being furthered in the research of Efilena Baseta (ESR07), where she is currently developing a 1:1 scale robotically fabricated timber

FIG. Saman Saffarian presents his prototype on the Midterm Review

structure, that in a controlled way can dynamically shape-shift. At KTH, Vasily Sitnikov (ESR09) has been developing simulations of ice erosion in conversation with Pablo Miranda Carranza. In his research project, ice is used for the production of CNC-milled ice formwork for a sustainable fabrication of non-standard concrete elements.

Many of the ESRs have produced papers and presented their research at conferences during this early fall, for example at the Design Modelling Symposium in Paris, eCAADe in Rome, IBPSA in San Fransisco, at IASS in Hamburg and at ACADIA in Cambridge. As the research projects by the ESRs have reached a level of maturity, we have seen more demonstrators produced and disseminated through conferences and exhibitions.

The Innochain network and programme has a focus on three main fields; Communicating design, Simulation for design, Materialising design. We are now seeing synergies between these fields where both computation and material feedback are central to the unfolding of the research. We are very proud to present the current state of the research by each of the ESRs in Innochain Network Journal #3.

The Editors:
Professor U. Karlsson, V Sitnikov

Midterm Review

2-3 JULY 2017

IAAC, VALLDAURA

FIG. Midterm Review Opening

Midterm Review: Focusing a training environment for interdisciplinary design collaboration

Martin Tamke (Project Coordinator, CITA)

The Midterm Review of the Innochain Network on July 3rd in the IAAC Self Sufficient Labs in Valldaura was a pinnacle event within the project. It was much anticipated, well prepared and finally a very positive and insightful event, which helped to focus the efforts of all partners involved in the project - whether ESR, University or Industry Partner.

The preparation of the event took months of efforts of the whole consortium, not at least as the working method of Innochain - the closeness to material and processes of design and making- require an extra effort in order to comply to the often more formal and standardised procedures within the European Commission. However our EU-officer was very welcoming towards new ideas regarding the presentation of the projects. These took finally part within the exhibition of the material probes. The team at IAAC organised the preparation of the exhibition and the venue in an excellent way and the venue at Valldaura with its rustic stone walls and historic atmosphere provided an excellent foundation for the high flying ideas and technologies presented in material probes, posters and videos. The setting in the mountains atop of Barcelona

created immediately a welcoming atmosphere, not at least through the possibility to provide an environment in which the many accompanying family members and kids in the network could have fun, while the Innochain Members were examined.

The midterm review marks a crucial point in the communication of the Innochain network with the funding agency at the European Commission. It is in fact the only time in the project period, where opinions of the achieved and the further steps can be exchanged in a personal way. A recognizable and very distinct difference in the assessment of the Innovative Training Network Innochain in regards to other research projects, was the focus on the individual Early Stage researchers and their projects. Rather than setting the main focus on the achievement of milestones and technical breakthroughs, the quality of learning, personal motivation and relevance and future trajectory in the field were highlighted. This emphasis on the future perspective was reassuring for the network and reflects well the aim of Innochain, to "train a new generation of interdisciplinary researchers with a strong industry focus that can effect real changes in the way we think, design and build our physical environment."

The network is now moving into its second half and the Early Stage Researchers and their projects have reached a level of maturity, which promises to make a real contribution to the field. The reviewers in Valldaura highlighted this fact and the interest, which Innochain generates in wider areas of the Industry is equally hinting on the increasing impact of the network.

Midterm Review: Exhibition

MIDTERM REVIEW

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fig. Midterm Review: Chiara Caseta (BSR07) present her project

FIG. ESR13 - Applied Robotics - Controlled Material Deposition; author: Arthur Prior

FIG. ESR09 - Simulating Concrete Formwork; author: Vasily Sitnikov

FIG. ESR15 - Small Scale Robotics - Manufacturing for the Large Scale Building; author: Stephanie Chattiel

FIG. ESR06 - Multi Scalar Modelling for Building Design; author: Paul Poinet

FIG. ESR02 - Integrating Material Performance; author: Tom Svilans

FIG. ESR08 - Virtual Prototyping FRP; author: James Solly

FIG. ESR10 - Simulating Robotic Feedback; author: Giulio Brugnaro

Innochain Workshop-Seminars

4-7 JULY 2017

IAAC, BARCELONA

TUTORS: PABLO MIRANDA CARRANZA;
ALEXANDRE DUBOR; RAIMUND KRENMÜLLER;
DAMJAN MINOVSKI

JURY MEMBERS: EDOUARD CABAY; ENRIC RUIZ
GELI; PHIL AYERS

LECTURES: SAM WILKINSON; PHIL AYERS;
SEBASTIAN RISI

Workshop-seminar 2.1

Communicating design

Topic: DESIGN COMMUNICATION IN SHARED VIRTUAL SPACE

Workshop lead: DAMJAN MINOVSKI

Participants:

EVY SLABBINCK (ESR01)
TOM SVILANS (ESR02)
ZEYNEP AKSOZ (ESR04)
DIMITRIE STEFANESCU (ESR05)

Workshop aims:

The workshop presents key problems of interdisciplinary collaboration that characterise working across the digital chain. It presents tools for shared prototyping and hybrid modelling enabling the integration of domain specific knowledge into common design platforms. The workshop is contextualised by a seminar with invited researchers reviewing results and presenting examples of collaborative processes. Collaboration and teamwork in the domain of design is a process involving a great amount of communication, organization and first and foremost, sketching. For architects the tool of choice was, and still is the tracing paper roll, where designs can be iterated, and several people can contribute by adding yet another layer, sketching out their ideas.

Still no digital tool has come close to the level of interactivity and flexibility when there is the need to consolidate ideas and thoughts of many participants.

The proposal for this workshop is a (team-)workflow experiment: A plugin for Rhino3d was developed by the workshop leader, that is probably best described as a 'Rhino-Multiplayer'. Each participant has one computer running Rhino and they are all connected in the same virtual environment through the above mentioned plugin. Every action they take (e.g. create a box, sphere etc.) is directly reflected on all other participating machines.

During the workshop we had multiple 'Sessions' where we tested different strategies of collaborative modeling. Starting without any specific goal, the first rounds were to familiarize the participants with the tool and also with each other in terms of modeling. 'Four musicians that never collaborated before have a jam session' could be an analogy. The first results were quite chaotic and hard to read, also because of the lack of any clear aim.

During the following days a rudimentary workflow and ruleset emerged. Each session was between 30 and 180 minutes and had a simple title / aim. In the beginning animals (Elephant, Giraffe) were chosen, because everyone had a similar notion of what it means, as opposed to terms like 'building'. While the proposition of four people simultaneously modeling an elephant in a CAD-application may sound wacky, it was a successful way to gain insight on potential applications and rules that would be needed for more serious work. In later iterations more architectural tasks were tried out, but due to the different backgrounds and specializations of the participants the results were not convincing.

FIG. LEFT Result of a session, aim: random

FIG. RIGHT Result of a session, aim: house

In conclusion the workshop was only partly a success, mainly because in its current version the tool is aimed to assist with early stages of design and sketching, which is hard to simulate in a workshop environment, and furthermore at the final review the feedback ranged from confusion to resentment.

FIG. TOP Result of a session, aim: church

Workshop-seminar 2.2

Simulation For Design

Topic: SIMULATION FUNDAMENTALS - THE LATTICE

Workshop lead: PABLO MIRANDA

Participants:

ANGELOS CHRONIS (ESR03)
PAUL POINET (ESR06)
EFILENA BASETA (ESR07)
JAMES SOLLY (ESR08)
VASILY SITNIKOV (ESR09)
STEPHANIE CHALTIEL(ESR15)

Workshop aims:

The workshop will explore the technological and conceptual basis that make computer simulations possible, in particular the process of discretisation of both space and time necessary in any computer simulation (Winsberg EB. Science in the age of computer simulation, 2010). As a specific study case the workshop will look at lattices and cellular decompositions, common in for example Cellular Automata: first proposed by John von Neumann during the late 1940s, lattices are still central to many forms of simulations, from fluid dynamics to models of urban growth.

The workshop will make use of coding in Processing as the means to test the possibilities and constraints of lattice based discretisations; the results will consist of text in the form of literate programming, that is, a mix of regular explanations and computer code, together with 3D printed models of the outputs.

While lattices may be well suited to some of the specific simulations of the participants, the main goal of the workshop is to understand the basic constraints computation imposes on simulation, in particular the problem of discretisation. The understanding of these constraints will then hopefully help to reflect on the distinct cases of each of the individual projects.

The main goal of the workshop was to discuss problems of discretisation through the use of cellular automata, linked to the specific modelling and simulations of the workshop participants. The use of cellular automata proved useful in a few cases as in the exploration of melting in concrete formwork made of ice in the case of Vasily Sitnikov, or in applying visualisation techniques to lattice based fluid dynamics models already in use by Angelos Chronis. Other researchers used the workshop to propose and test alternative discretisation models for their respective research domains: spring models to dynamically simulate anisotropic wood bending by Efilena Baseta, or the application of physic engines from game and animation software for the virtual prototyping of filament structures by James Solly. Paul Poinet continued examining the hierarchical subdivision and organisation of multi-scalar representations of building processes, and Stephanie Chaltiel translated some of the concerns of her research into the notation systems of the Processing programming language. The participants took the main themes of the workshop and successfully integrate them with the concerns of their research projects. Besides specific

FIG. LEFT Analyzing a diffusion model based Turing's Reaction-Diffusion Equation (V. Sitnikov)

FIG. RIGHT A still frame from an animation of a diffusion process applied to a three-dimensional system (V. Sitnikov)

details related to the particular work of the researchers, as a workshop leader the most important outcome was pedagogical and research-methodological: the particular case of involving other researchers and peers with very specific and developed research concerns, rather than architectural students, provided a useful experience in formulating similar design-based research workshops in the future.

```

TuringReactDiff___melting | Processing 3.3.5
File Edit Sketch Debug Tools Help

TuringReactDiff___melting
26 }
27
28 void iterate() {
29     // uses Euler's method to solve the diff eqns
30
31     for(int i=0; i<h; ++i) {
32
33         // treat the surface as a torus by wrapping at the edges
34         int iplus1 = wrap(i+1,w);
35         int iminus1 = wrap(i-1,w);
36
37         for(int j=0; j<w; ++j) {
38
39             int jplus1 = wrap(j+1,h);
40             int jminus1 = wrap(j-1,h);
41
42             //These are the reaction-diffusion equations
43
44             // Component A
45             float DiA = CA * ( Ao[iplus1][j] + Ao[iminus1][j] + Ao[i][jplus1]
46             float ReA = Ao[i][j] * Bo[i][j] - Ao[i][j] - 9; // [-9; 81]
47
48

```

FIG. TOP Processing interface

Workshop-seminar 2.3

Materialising Design

Topic: EXTENDING THE 3D-PRINTING VOCABULARY
BY INVESTIGATING NEW CAPABILITIES

Workshop lead:
ALEXANDRE DUBOR
RAIMUND KRENMÜLLER

Participants:
GIULIO BRUGNARO (ESR10)
HELENA WESTERLIND (ESR11)
SAMAN SAFFARIAN (ESR12)
ARTHUR PRIOR (ESR13)

Workshop aims:

The basis of this workshop is an approach that integrates the hands-on use of the hardware tools, as well as the development of the computational design tools necessary to control the newly introduced parameters. For this reason the following topics are proposed:

- 1. Multi-material printing:** by using a 2-component extruder, we will experiment with gradients and regions of varying material properties.
- 2. 5-Axis printing & discontinuous deposition:** by going beyond the usual strategy of continuously layering horizontal cross-sections of parts, we seek to extend the existing vocabulary of 3d-printing in terms of the process itself and the expression of the product. To that aim, 5 axes (XYZAB) and discontinuous material deposition strategies will be explored.
- 3. Hybrid manufacturing:** by combining additive and subtractive manufacturing, parts (or buildings) with differentiated surface textures and scales of precision can be produced. We will investigate the aesthetic and functional implications of this hybrid process.
- 4. Sensor feedback & Behavioural control:** by incorporating sensor data, production processes can adapt to conditions unknown prior to their execution and can be determined as abstract behaviour instead of rigid instructions. Neural networks are a way to represent behaviour as a pattern of connectivity between sensory input and actuator output. We aim to explore in simulated and physical space how the concept of behaviour can be used in the creation of form.

From the proposed topics, the ESRs showed the most interest in “sensor feedback and behavioural control”. Three exercises were set up that relate to the ESRs’ individual research focus:

Stone scan - Helena Westerlind

In this exercise, we established a process in which a human designer and an industrial robot cooperate in the production of a layered structure made from stones with clay acting as a binder. The robot would lay out a curve using a clay extruder, on which the human collaborator arranges stones of unknown geometry. In the next step, the resulting structure is scanned, using a microsoft kinect. By filtering and analyzing the point cloud obtained from the scan using rhino/grasshopper, a toolpath is created. The robot then follows this toolpath in the next pass to add the clay binder.

The iterative process created in this project raised new opportunity for a Human-Machine collaboration where masonry craftsmen could combine their skills with advances in 3D printing and digital design optimisation.

FIG. LEFT Fast Fourier Waveform Analysis used to identify the depth of a milling path (G.Brugnaro and S. Safarian)

FIG. RIGHT Temperature profile of an extrusion pass collected with an infrared sensor (A. Prior and A.Scherer)

Listening to wood - Giulio Brugnaro and Saman Saffarian

Wood is an example of a material with a heterogenous structure that is often ignored in industrial processing, but plays an important role in traditional craftsmanship. This notion is at the core of Giulio’s research and is also reflected in the project we set up during the innochain workshop. In milling wood, a correct set of parameters will result in less vibrations and an acoustic signature that experienced machine operators will easily recognize as “right”. This observation gave rise to the idea of using acoustic data from a contact microphone directly mounted to the workpiece to control the milling parameters such as feed rate and spindle speed. A test piece was produced successfully using the shopbot CNC machine where a Fast Fourier sound analysis was used to define the depth of cut of the local milling path.

This material feedback integration in the milling process could give rise to optimised milling time for heterogeneous materials, but also could be exploited as an artistic feature where the intrinsic properties of the materials have their says in the final outcome of the process.

Temperature probes - Arthur Prior and Annie-Locke Scherer

The wax used in Arthur’s research depends on specific thermal conditions to properly bind to the previous layers in the 3d-printing process. We’ve used an infrared sensor mounted on industrial robot and connected to an Arduino board to log a temperature profile of an extrusion pass (represented by a line of nichrome wire heated by electrical current), which can then be incorporated in Arthur’s printing process to control extrusion parameters on the fly. Potentials were foreseen to improve the reliability of the wax printing process by extracting live data with this contact-less sensors.

Activity Reports

- WP3 - COMMUNICATING DESIGN
- WP4 - SIMULATING DESIGN
- WP5 - MATERIALISING DESIGN

FIG. ESR15 Controlled Material Deposition, author: Arthur Prior

Multiple states of equilibrium for bending-active (tensile) structures

EVY SLABBINCK

ESR NUMBER: ESR01

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: McNeel, Foster + Partners

INSTITUTE: ITKE

FIG. Render of the BAT_01 by S. Suzuki and E. Slabbinck

MULTIPLE STATES OF EQUILIBRIUM FOR BENDING-ACTIVE (TENSILE) STRUCTURES

The last 6 months were mainly focused on the development of the ICD/ITKE Research Pavilion 2017/2018. This pavilion is a demonstrator that is proof of concept for adaptive and evolving bending-active tensile (BAT) structures. The project involves researcher from both ICD (Institute for Computational Design and Construction) and ITKE (Institute of Building Structures and Structural Design) and a group of students of the ITECH master programme. This researcher guides the structural team and is responsible for the structural design concept. The construction of the pavilion is planned for March 2018. The pavilion is one of the several planned case studies for the use of multiple states of equilibrium for bending-active tensile hybrid structures.

A collaboration with ITKE researcher, Seiichi Suzuki, in the last year allows the development of a workflow from design to analysis for these highly complex BAT structures with their reciprocal equilibrium and third order non-linear analysis. A pavilion was proposed to test out the proposed interface: the BAT_01. This work can hopefully be presented at the Innochain exhibition in Barcelona early next year.

Next to the work on the pavilion and BAT_01, several papers were written for IASS 2017, a symposium focussing on spatial and shell structures. The papers are focussing on several aspects of bending-active tensile structures i.e. topological design, cataloguing different structural systems and the use of torsion and multiple states of equilibrium. This work was presented at the conference this September.

Several workshops, e.g. Innochain Midterm Review in Barcelona, Winter school in Berlin, etc. and visits with the industry partners during the last half a year provided better framing of the research and guidance to a focussed development of the topic.

Further research involves the close collaboration with industry partner Foster + Partners, and more specific the Specialist Modelling Group (SMG). The research looks into the development of applications for using multiple states of equilibrium, or simple adaptive, bending-active tensile structures and break out of the academic bubble. The advantages of these structures are compared to other spatial, lightweight and conventional structures.

FIG. DIAGRAM SHOWING MULTIPLE STATES OF EQUILIBRIUM DURING CONSTRUCTION FOR BAT STRUCTURES BY E. SLABBINCK ET AL.

FIG. E. Slabbinck presenting at the exhibition in Vienna

Integrating Material Performance

TOM SVILANS

ESR NUMBER: ESR02

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Blumer Lehmann, WHITE

INSTITUTE: CITA

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FIG. Sensor prototype, Blumer Lehmann AG, Gossau

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ACTIVITY REPORTS

This period of time for this project was mostly taken up by the first industry secondment, experimentation back in Copenhagen afterwards, and preparations for the second industry secondment. After the Innochain colloquium, I moved to Gossau, Switzerland to spend a couple of months working with Blumer-Lehmann to integrate scanning and feedback technologies into their glulam production. Central to the secondment was the question of how this type of research can be conducted alongside an active, constantly-running production process. The method which we decided upon was one of developing tests and ‘shadowing’ the production until a point, then testing the implementation on the production line, with a way to simply rollback the changes if it was not performing as expected or improving the process. This allowed us to test different scanning and measuring processes in a quick way, with minimal impact on the active production cycle, and then directly implement some of those processes when they were found to be beneficial. This piecemeal strategy meant that, once there was a positive effect on the production, it could be immediately integrated and used, leading to very tangible impacts of the research on the industry process. The secondment concluded with

leaving a prototype laser scanner with Blumer Lehmann for their use on future projects, a set of case-studies exploring different scanning and capture techniques using building components and data from the active production, and a 2-day meeting with both industry partners and academic supervisors at Blumer Lehmann to discuss future work and collaborations.

After the first secondment, I implemented some of the tools and strategies we developed for Blumer Lehmann back in the CITA workshop. Workflows for generating the type of production data required for free-form timber components were overhauled and some new machining setups were tried out to increase the flexibility and capacity for us to form and machine free-form glulams at CITA. Scanning was integrated in a much more solid way, with automation and speed of turnaround as the main priorities. The link between scanning, registration, and machining was made much more robust, allowing us to speed up the exchange between scan result and next machining steps. This is also something to be developed further, perhaps to see how a breakdown of machining operations into finer segments driven by iterative scanning feedback could help the idea of a 'soft fabrication model'. The previous demonstrator from this spring was revived and reconsidered using these approaches, leading to a couple of improved material studies of one of the elements.

In tandem with this development and experimentation, the summer was spent preparing for the second secondment at White Arkitekter, which has now begun in October. I was introduced to the Dsearch framework and methodology, as well as several projects with which I am now working. The objective is to explore the world of 'early-stage design' and see how the research project (and, generally, what I have learned) can impact, guide, or inform some emerging timber-based projects.

FIG. PROJECT ENVIRONMENT, CITA, COPENHAGEN

Integrating Building Physics for Performance Control

ANGELOS CHRONIS

ESR NUMBER: ESR03

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: McNeel, Foster + Partners

INSTITUTE: IAAC

FIG. Integration of CFD in Computational Design

During the last six months, the project has focused on the development of the skills and tools for the CFD integration, the secondment at McNeel and dissemination of the research and design probes already produced.

The first secondment at McNeel Europe started around the end of March and it has been instrumental in understanding the potential for development of CFD integration tools for computational design. Meetings with McNeel experts along with the collaboration with two leading development teams, i.e. the development team of RhinoCFD (leading CFD integration for Rhino) and the developers of the Butterfly add-on for Grasshopper (leading CFD integration for OpenFOAM and Grasshopper) have helped to clearly establish the state of the art and the value of the project's involvement in these developments. The McNeel secondment, which is intermittently still ongoing has been very helpful in roadmapping the further development of the project. More recently, initial meetings were done to organize the second secondment, with Foster+Partners, with very fruitful meetings with the specialist teams there (SMG and Environmental Engineering groups) which helped find common

ground for further collaboration (involvement in developing and assessing their OpenFOAM workflow).

During both the secondment at McNeel and the intermittent time, the focus has been on developing necessary programming skills to enable the development of integration tools, such as OpenFOAM trainings, Butterfly trainings, RhinoCFD training and fundamental programming training. Further to that, a number of student as well as architectural projects presented opportunities for testing and applying the CFD integration efforts. At the moment, the project is involved in an ongoing collaboration with Fender Katsalides architects, who are looking for a shape optimization workflow for their tower designs, a collaboration with a Civil Engineering student from the University of Patras, whose thesis is focused on using CFD for creating natural ventilation potential in the complex urban fabric of Athens and in organizing two CFD-related workshops, one at TU Graz and one at the ESR's host university, IaaC.

Further to the development of the project, the research findings and design probes that have already been developed within the project were presented in three different conferences, namely the "Design Modeling Symposium" where a paper titled "Energy Efficient Design for 3D Printed Earth Architecture" and the eCAADe (Educational and research in Computer Aided Architectural Design in Europe) conference in Rome, where two papers titled "Digital fabrication with Virtual and Augmented Reality for Monolithic Shells" and "Integration of CFD in Computational Design - An evaluation of the current state of the art" were presented. The latter paper is co-authored with Mostapha Roudsari, the main developer of Ladybug tools, which includes Butterfly and a very prominent researcher in the field. During this period, a number of other research papers, co-authored by the ESR were also presented at these conferences as well as the SimAUD conference in Toronto, the CAADFutures conference in Istanbul, the IBPSA conference in San Francisco. A total of 10 papers were presented during this period.

FIG. FAST FLUID DYNAMICS INTEGRATION IN GRASSHOPPER

FIG. MESHING COMPARISON BETWEEN CFD TOOLS

Multi-Criteria Optimisation in Early Design Phase

ZEYNEP AKSOZ

ESR NUMBER: ESR04

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: STR.UCTURE, BIG

INSTITUTE: IOA

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ACTIVITY REPORTS

INTERACTIVE MULTIPLE CRITERIA SEARCH FOR PERFORMANCE AWARE EARLY DESIGN

This research project searches for methods to generate more diverse design variations in the early design phase by informing the user on the design performance of each variation. Within the timespan of the project different methods within the field of artificial intelligence are investigated to extend the design space in interaction with the users input. This way a new design methodology is developed that combines the human and artificial intelligence. As a result, the artificial intelligence becomes an extension of designer's creativity, allowing the designer to navigate solutions that might not be directly accessible by designer's own abilities. Within this framework questions regarding the possibilities of different interaction processes are raised to maximize designer's input to the collaborative design process. Increasing the designer's input would allow the designer to be more active within this design process, on the other hand the computers knowledge on the problem statement can be further extended and by accessing more accurate information the generalization problems of Machine Learning can be solved.

By allowing the designer to interact with the computer in different ways the collaborative design process will not only be limited to digital environment. In this phase the possibilities of working with physical design artefacts were investigated. The experiment was aiming to learn from the designer's tacit knowledge by analyzing physical models and their performances created by the designers, to design new artefacts using artificial intelligence that base on the extracted rules and patterns from physical environment.

The experiment was conducted during an artist in residency month in September 2017 in IaaC Barcelona in collaboration with the tutors of Open Thesis Fabrication(OTF) Program Edouard Cabay, Alexandre Dubor, Kunal Chandra and the students of this program.

The students were asked to design 'Zeer Pots', which is a pot in pot cooling system, which is working with evaporative cooling principle. This system consists of two clay pots where the smaller pot is placed in a larger one. The space in between the pots is filled with sand. The system is activated with deposition of water into the sand layer, when the water starts to evaporate, the surfaces of both pots start to cool down, which ends up in cooling the inner pot. This system is mainly used for alternative refrigeration in hot and dry climates. In this exercise the students were designing only the outer pots to increase the cooling performance on the surface and in the inner pot. Designs were printed with a Kuka Robot, and baked in a ceramic oven. To test the cooling performance of each pot a Thermal Imaging Camera (in this case Flir One) was used to document the cooling process on the surface and a moisture and temperature sensor was used to record the temperature within the inner pot.

This kind of design problems are hard to simulate digitally, since the design performance depend on the complex relations of certain morphologic features, material properties, environmental properties. To understand the performance a design, fabricate and analyze workflow should be followed. This would be a very long process to understand the behavior adjust the digital model

accordingly and iterate the fabrication to analyze again. However, by using machine learning we were able to create a short cut, that can predict the behavior of certain geometric features digitally. This way, we could approximate the performance of new design variations within the digital environment.

In the further extension of the experiment an evolutionary learning method was used to develop new designs basing on the relationship between morphology and performance. In this case a neural network was trained to learn from the design decisions of the students. Each design was exploded into a point cloud and each point of each design was analyzed by the local shape feature of this point regarding temperature performance. This way the evolutionary learning algorithm could extract patterns that relate shape feature and performance at any location of the design. Learning from the student designs the computer was asked to develop new designs. As a result, the new designs developed by the computer were far more complex than the student designs but behaving similarly or sometimes better.

Alternate Means to Communicate Measure

DIMITRIE STEFANESCU

ESR NUMBER: ESR05

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: HENN

INSTITUTE: Bartlett

During the last few months, I have been working on solidifying my research on both the technical front as well as positioning it within the wider context, both academic and industrial. I have noticed an increased attention and encouragement coming from industry partners which see the potential in the output from my research as challenging existing design communication paradigms (BIM) and helping improve communication flows alongside the whole value chain.

This has led to a clear problem definition regarding the issues surrounding digital design data communication and the positioning my efforts towards pursuing basic research into the development of Speckle as a reliable, open, low-level domain specific data transfer layer for the AEC industry. Going further, this protocol can serve as a foundation for the development of numerous other applications, ranging from reporting and scheduling to machine learning and augmented reality.

As part of the development effort, there have been several iterations of the Speckle platform, going through three minor releases from

0.0.1 to 0.0.3. Furthermore, I have written a series (still in progress) of documentation articles explaining some of the technical points behind the protocol and platform, which can be seen here: <https://speckle.works/doc/>. Alongside this curated list of articles, I have published the full Speckle API documentation at <https://speckleworks.github.io/SpeckleOpenApi/> which is more appealing for the power users and the technically oriented audience.

During my secondments at HENN and McNeel I have been actively involved in deploying and testing the protocol and its existing implemented plugins, as well as actively researching into applying the existing base functionality towards new application domains. This ongoing process is essential to fully defining the problems of design communication and as well the way in which we can technologically respond and alleviate the main friction points. Innovation does not happen in isolation. All parts of the Speckle software ecosystem are released under the most permissive open source license (MIT) in order to both encourage collaboration and proprietary extensions and private, for-profit deployment. I have set up a github organisation that transparently controls all access to code repositories and now numbers seven contributors and nine repositories. The community Slack group grew from 14 to 84 people from various backgrounds.


```

FOLDERS
  SpeckleServer
  .config
  app
  api
  core
  accounts
  clients
  comments
  objects
  streams
  layers
    LayerDeleteObj
    LayerGetObject
    LayerPostObj
    LayerPutObj
    LayersDelete.js
    LayersGet.js
    LayerSingleDelete
    LayerSingleGet
    LayerSinglePatch
    LayerSinglePut
    LayersPatch.js
    LayersPost.js
    LayersPut.js
    NameGet.js
    NamePut.js
    ObjectDelete.js
    ObjectsDelete.js
    ObjectsGet.js
    ObjectsPost.js
    ObjectsPut.js
    StreamDelete.js
    StreamDiff.js
    StreamDuplicate.js
    StreamGet.js
    StreamPost.js
    StreamPut.js

LayerPostObjects.js --- speckleserver
8 const SpeckleObject = require( '../models/SpeckleObject' )
9
10 module.exports = ( req, res ) => {
11
12   if ( !req.params.streamId ) {
13     res.status( 400 )
14     return res.send( { success: false, message: 'No stream id provided.' } )
15   }
16   let dbStream = [
17     let targetLayer = {
18     DataStream.findOne( { streamId: req.params.streamId } )
19     .then( stream => {
20       if ( !stream ) throw new Error( 'No stream found.' )
21       if ( stream.private && !req.user ) throw new Error( 'Unauthorized. Please log in.' )
22       if ( stream.private && ( !req.user || !req.user.id.equals( stream.owner ) ) || stream.sharedWith
23         throw new Error( 'Unauthorized. Please log in.' )
24
25       let layer = stream.layers.find( l => l.guid === req.params.layerId )
26       if ( !layer ) layer = stream.layers.find( l => l.name === req.params.layerId )
27       if ( !layer ) throw new Error( 'No layer with that id/name found.' )
28
29       dbStream = stream
30       targetLayer = layer
31       return Promise.all( req.body.objects.reduce( ( arr, o ) => ( o._id !== undefined && o.type === '
32     ) )
33     .then( () => SpeckleObject.find( { hash: { $in: req.body.objects.reduce( ( arr, o ) => o._id ===
34     ) } )
35     .then( results => {
36       results.forEach( o => req.body.objects.filter( oo => oo.hash === o.hash ).forEach( oo => oo._id =
37     )
38     return SpeckleObject.insertMany( req.body.objects.filter( so => so._id !== undefined ) )
39     .then( results => {
40       results.forEach( o => req.body.objects.filter( oo => oo.hash === o.hash ).forEach( oo => oo._id =
41     )
42     module.exports = mongoose.model(
9
10 private: { type: Boolean, default: false }
11 sharedWith: [ { type: mongoose.Schema.Types.ObjectId, ref: 'User' } ]
12 // should replace 'sharedWith'
13 canRead: [ { type: mongoose.Schema.Types.ObjectId, ref: 'User' } ]
14 canWrite: [ { type: mongoose.Schema.Types.ObjectId, ref: 'User' } ]
15 canComment: [ { type: mongoose.Schema.Types.ObjectId, ref: 'User' } ]
16 name: { type: String, default: '' }
17 baseProperties: { type: Object, default: {} }
18 globalMeasures: { type: Object, default: {} }
19 isComputedResult: { type: Boolean, default: false }
20 objects: [ { type: mongoose.Schema.Types.ObjectId, ref: 'Object' } ]
21 layers: { type: Array, default: [] }
22 parent: { type: String, default: '' }
23 children: { type: Array, default: [] }
24 comments: [ { type: mongoose.Schema.Types.ObjectId, ref: 'Comment' } ]
25 deleted: { type: Boolean, default: false }
26 ], { timestamps: true } )
27
28 module.exports = mongoose.model(

```

Furthermore, I have been actively nurturing both internal (within InnoChain, namely: HENN, McNeel, Buro Happold, Design-To-Production) and external (outside InnoChain, namely: ARUP, Turner Construction, Woods Bagot) industry and academic connections that have been aggregating around my research development effort for an open design data communication protocol and ecosystem. My hope is that these efforts will lead towards securing a sustainable future for the field of design communication, whose importance is now finally being revealed and understood.

Multi Scalar Modelling for Building Design

PAUL POINET

ESR NUMBER: ESR06

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Buro Happold, DesignToProduction

INSTITUTE: CITA

FIG.1 - "LAYER STALKER" - RHINOCEROS PLUG-IN BASED ON A D3JS RADIAL TIDY DREE.

During the period of March-October 2017, my initial research questions have been reformulated in order to tackle the existing challenges faced in industry regarding data management across multiple scales:

- How can we identify, access and communicate implicit (and tacit) knowledge spread across the unrelated leaves of the directory structure, multiple scales and different trades?
- How can we keep track, add and modify data within a common directory structure until completion of the building?
- How would an ideal multi-scalar parametric AEC-model look like and which requirements would it have to fulfill all user's requests? How could the multi-scalar model be interacted and which UI and UX concepts would be needed?

During the period of March 2017 - October 2017, I have been investigating the organization of data structures from different files at Design-To-Production. This helped to the following development and production of different software tools helping the expert user to get a better overview of the data that (s)he is working with. Those tools have been further extended with user experience (UX) features, where more intuitive interaction with the Rhino layer table has been made possible (see picture below).

These UX features enabled the user to query any keyword that can be checked against all layer names. If a match is found, the objects contained within the highlighted layer(s) would be displayed. Of course, such interface is only useful if the data is organized specifically within the specific layer table of Rhino3d. Therefore, further research has looked at how to generalize such processes through more generic means (e.g. databases).

During my last secondment (September 2017) at Buro Happold in September, I had the opportunity to observe advanced design workflows where data could be sent, received and filtered through different software platforms using the BHoM (Bureau Habitat object Model). A centralized database containing all geometrical information through abstract notations – strings, hashes or primitive geometries (points, lines, etc.) – could be accessed by any other co-worker of the company who could retrieve specific information and continue to work within its own software/environment.

Around the same period (September-October 2017), I also started to collaborate with Dimitrie Stefanescu (ESR 5), using the openAPI of Speckle which offers a very similar framework to BHoM where objects can be stored, filtered, queried and accessed within a centralized database. Building workflows on top of this framework, I have been investigating files from Design-To-Production as a case study. Those files contain a large amount of objects with their corresponding attributes that are particularly important in order to communicate specific information with the different trades involved in the design process at late stages. I demonstrated the possibility of transferring large groups of objects containing many different types & attributes (groups, names, user strings, colors, etc.) stored within different layers through user-specified streams without any loss of information. Those objects can then be filtered (based on any attached properties) and recreated within another file (located within the same server and within another client).

Future work will look at how to combine UI/UX experience (Fig.1) and data transferring/querying/filtering strategies (Fig.2) so that the user (and/or expert user) can generate, classify and filter data in the most meaningful way.

FIG.2 - RHINO-TO-RHINO URL WORKFLOW USING A LOCAL SPECKLE SERVER + ITS CORRESPONDING OPENAPI

Simulating Anisotropic Material

EFILENA BASETA

ESR NUMBER: ESR07

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Cloud9, Blumer Lehmann

INSTITUTE: IOA

FIG. 1 - CONCEPT DIAGRAM

DYNAMIC ACTIVE BENDING STRUCTURES

Dynamic architecture has a wide spectrum of applications from sliding interior partitions to automated switching of lightings and media facades. In this research, the meaning of dynamicity focuses on spatial formations of bendable materials, whose applications are not limited to facade systems or small scale experimental structures but can have high structural performance. (Fig. 1)

Evaluating existing micro (nanometer) and meso (decimeter) scalar, natural and synthetic, self-actuated mechanisms as well as results from personal experiments on the hygroscopic behaviour of wood veneer, I concluded that the performance of dynamic material systems depends on the relation between their rigidly connected parts. More specifically these systems consist of minimum two parts: the active, which responds to the stimuli (e.g. humidity) and the resistive, which regulates this response (Fig. 2).

In the attempt to scale up this dynamic behaviour in macroscale (meter) I translated the aforementioned principle, so as it consists of two active parts which are not rigidly connected. The fluctuating connectivity between the active parts plays the role of the resistive part of the micro-meso scalar mechanisms, therefore it defines the performance and the deformation of the system. In this case the stimuli are forces that are induced by external parameters (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2 - SYSTEM PRINCIPLE

Consequently, the proposed system is based on active bending structures which can dynamically fluctuate between the flat and the maximum bent form, depending on the external force applied to the system and the internal forces of the material itself. This agrees with D' Arcy Thompson's idea, who believes that "The form is a system which organises itself in the presences of both internal and external forces [...]".

In this framework, this research focuses on the creation of controllable dynamic active bending structures, using forces as the actuators. More specifically it seeks for new ways of experimenting with linear elements, where the connections between them define the overall deformation of the system. This allows for scalable and easily erected actively bending structures.

FIG. 3 - LATHS BENDING TEST

FIG. 4 - MAX BENDING OF LATHS

Wood becomes an important case study material for the suggested system as it is a natural fibrous composite, whose fibers' orientation define its flexibility. Therefore wood, in different configurations and forms can behave either as a flexible or as a very rigid material. Most architectural applications of wood look for stiff elements but examples from vernacular architecture as well as recent researches on active bending structures indicate the great potential of perceiving wood as a highly flexible material, which can be used for light weight, free form structures. Nonetheless, there is no example in architecture where wood is dynamically active, functioning as a reactive compliant mechanism.

Therefore, initial physical and digital tests on dynamically active bending wooden laths (Fig. 3,4) and lattices (Fig. 5) have been conducted in collaboration with my industrial partner, Blumer Lehmann, in order to understand the material behaviour. Currently I am working on producing a 1:1 scale, robotically fabricated (Fig. 6), timber structure, that can dynamically shape-shift between different controlled forms.

FIG. 5 - ACTIVE BENDING LATTICE

FIG.6 - ROBOTIC FABRICATION OF DYNAMIC ACTIVE WOODEN BEAMS

Virtual Prototyping FRP

JAMES SOLLY

ESR NUMBER: ESR08

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: S-Form, Foster+

INSTITUTE: ITKE

FIG.1 –LOCAL FIBRE ARRANGEMENT, ICD/ITKE RESEARCH PAVILION
2016/2017 © ICD/ITKE

The end of March and beginning of April saw the final stages of fabrication of the ICD/ITKE Research Pavilion 2016/2017 then its transportation and installation outside the Faculty of Architecture of the University of Stuttgart. This large scale technology demonstrator had been under development (of increasing intensity with time) since early 2016 by students on the ITECH master programme, guided by researchers from the ITKE and ICD. The project investigated the possibilities of long-span coreless fibre winding using multiple cooperating fabrication elements (industrial robots working alongside a drone and a fibre extrusion/tension-control system). This researcher supported the student group as they developed the highly-interlinked fibre placement sequence, geometry resulting from this and the structural design concept. The pavilion acts as a highly relevant case-study within the ongoing Virtual Prototyping FRP research project and a first paper on the project, written with the other project tutors, is being presented at the upcoming Acadia conference.

Directly following the unveiling of the pavilion, this researcher arranged the Innochain Materialising Design Seminar which

included the attendance of several ESRs at the Fabricate conference in Stuttgart, where a paper on the Elytra Pavilion (the demonstrator installed during 2016 at the V&A, London) was also presented. The Innochain Midterm Review in Barcelona provided further opportunity to refine the central concepts of the research topic and the following Workshop Seminar allowed for investigation of fibre simulation with physics libraries accessible via the Processing language.

Recent research progress has been guided by several visits to Foster + Partners. Working within the Specialist Modelling Group (SMG) both helped to contextualise the research within the growing field of additive manufacture for Architecture and provided technical assistance on areas of computational tool development. The SMG is working on several projects that consider the performance of additively-manufactured parts and how the specifics of toolpath planning can directly impact on performance of the resulting part. Involvement in these projects has helped to outline several requirements that would improve the adoption of coreless filament winding into future architectural development.

Through this period there has also been the opportunity to be involved as a thesis tutor on the ITECH master programme. Working with students interested in composite fabrication allowed for the investigation of several speculative possibilities for using fibre-based materials in construction and a consideration of what virtual prototyping strategies might be suitable for a variety of related, yet different, design processes. The outcomes of these research projects will be published shortly following their final examination. In the upcoming months, the intention is to complete and test several new iterations of a design tool for coreless-wound fibres and to test these, alongside optimisation strategies, on the development of prototypes for display at the Innochain exhibition in Barcelona in February.

FIG. 2 - DAYTIME VIEW, ICD/ITKE RESEARCH PAVILION
2016/2017 © ICD/ITKE

FIG. 3 - STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS WORKFLOW, ICD/ITKE RESEARCH PAVILION
2016/2017 © ICD/ITKE

Simulating Concrete Formwork

VASILY SITNIKOV

ESR NUMBER: ESR09

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Buro Happold

INSTITUTE: KTH

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FIG.1 – PICTURE OF A CONCRETE PROTOTYPE FABRICATED WITH #ICEFORMWORK

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#ICEFORMWORK FOR UHPC

The work conducted up until now has led to a concept of a new type of fabrication of structural concrete elements using ice as the formwork material. In the past period of 6 months the general preconditions that underlay the concept of #iceformwork have been studied, described and made public through a peer-reviewed article in proceedings of the Design Modelling Symposium 2017, and several public presentations and discussions. With the next step we are planning to publish our findings in the discipline of material science of concrete, providing results and analysis of several tests of UHPC hydration at negative temperature which have been already carried out and evaluated. This work is meant to reinforce the material theory of #iceformwork, e.g. fabrication of concrete elements at sub-freezing temperatures which can contribute to the relatively young branch of this material science.

In parallel, the computational side of the research has been pushed forward. The basic logical mechanism for simulation of ice erosion based on spatial lattices and CA algorithms has been constructed in conversation with Pablo Miranda Carranza during the Workshop-

FIG. 2 - CONCRETE CAST IS BEING RELEASED FROM THE ICE FORMWORK

seminar 2.2 Simulation for Design. The iterative numerical model of erosion is then visualized through the use of implicit surfaces (namely Marching Cubes algorithm) resulting in a polygonal mesh. Further elaboration took place during a period of secondments at Buro Happold Engineers. The core logic of structural topological optimization (namely Bi-directional Evolutionary Structural Optimization) based on finite element analysis has been assessed and translated to C# programming language for the purpose of further research and integration with other design software environment. The main goal of this computational research is to construct a design tool that is informed with the process of fabrication. This design tool can be defined as a combination of the erosion simulation (Fig. 3) and the structural analysis, where the reverse use of former algorithm is used to extract the simplest geometrical preconditions for the complex and doubly curved geometry of the latter.

The next series of material experiments will focus on imposing exact geometry on ice, that is on machining ice using CNC-router. This aspect of research requires a specific technical set up and

experimental machining equipment. For this purpose we have received funding from Helgo Zettervalls foundation. This grant will comprise the budget for initial construction and development of a CNC-router integrated in a chamber with constant negative temperature, to provide the necessary means for fabrication of ice formworks and concrete prototypes of a specific geometry. In further perspective it will help to study and measure the process of erosion and will contribute to the calibration of the simulation.

In the remaining time, the main attention will be dedicated to the assessment of feasibility and viability of the examined fabrication concept. The main interest is the relation between scale and energy consumption of the proposed fabrication system in respect to different local climate conditions. It is also interesting to compare it to the economy of the existing methods of fabrication (that is based mainly on the manual assembly of timber formworks) and to the new types of automated modes of production which are just about to appear in the niche of prefabricated concrete industry.

FIG. 3 - PRINCIPLE OF MELTING SIMULATION

Simulating Robotic Feedback

GIULIO BRUGNARO

ESR NUMBER: ESR10

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: BIG, ROK

INSTITUTE: Bartlett

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One of the key aspects of the research focuses on how we can encapsulate, at least partially, human instrumental knowledge in the technological means for fabrication currently available. An adaptive framework for subtractive robotic timber fabrication, using a set of traditional carving tools (chisel and gouges), has been developed to investigate whether this knowledge can be captured, transferred, and potentially augmented from the domain of human craftsmanship to robotic manufacturing. The proposition is that we can achieve this through a combination of different sensing strategies and machine learning procedures, such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN), as part of a predictive strategy to train the fabrication process to operate with a specific set of carving tools and wood types. In the last months, in the perspective of applying the developed framework in the collaboration with the industry partners, the work has focused specifically on the integration of the encapsulated instrumental knowledge in an interface that makes it available to designers. This allows to extend the design moment beyond the computer's screen and aim to explore novel design opportunities through the direct engagement with materials and manufacturing methods.

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The secondment at ROK has been organised in two different parts: an intense design stage of one month in Zurich and three months dedicated to the fabrication stage at the Bartlett School of Architecture in London where I have access to the robotic facilities offered by the BMADE Workshop. During the design stage in August, several potential applications have been discussed, also in regard to the tight time schedule available, ranging from furniture pieces to larger interior installations. The project we identified as the most promising for a direct application of the research consists in a large horizontal platform composed of different carved panels where different artistic plastic figures are going to be exhibited inside a new art gallery in Stuttgart. In the past month, several panels have been carved to test both research and design ideas while in the following weeks the fabrication of the actual components for the final piece will take place.

In parallel with the secondment, a series of three carved panels have been presented at the exhibition "Academic Platforms of Computational Design" at the Academy of Arts, Architecture and Design (UMPRUM) in Prague and the research has been discussed at the "ReseArch Conference" in conjunction with the event. Furthermore, the paper "Adaptive Robotic Training Methods for Subtractive Manufacturing", discussing the initial developments of

the methods and first results, has been accepted at the ACADIA Conference 2017 and will be presented at the beginning of November at the MIT in Cambridge (US).

Finally, while the fabrication stage for the project in collaboration with ROK is still going on, I'm currently discussing with BIG, and their department BIG IDEAS, how we can integrate the work done until now on robotic carving but also apply similar methods to other subtractive tools to further extend the range of manufacturing methods available in-house to their designers.

Controlled Deposition of Concrete

HELENA WESTERLIND

ESR NUMBER: ESR11

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: WHITE

INSTITUTE: KTH

CHOREOGRAPHING FLOW

The introduction of additive manufacturing in concrete construction challenges some of the principles that currently condition the use of concrete within the built environment; such as the dependence upon formwork and the tendency for standardisation and simplification of architectural elements. This research project is specifically concerned with how the technology can address the growing environmental impact of concrete production by contributing to a more efficient use of material resources. The specific mode of inquiry investigates how material properties can be adopted to match local performance requirements by varying the cement ratio and composition of the material in relation to deposition strategies.

In the past months the project has focused on the historic contexts of two of the trajectories driving the research, namely prefabricated construction and the material composition of concrete. The inquiry, titled 'The Liquid Stone Cookbook', traces an alternative history of concrete through historical recipes of liquid stone. Using the analogue of cooking, the study, situates the research within a

material practice that long predates modern science. Like cooking, the pursuit of liquid stone has largely been an empirical science, based on chance, testing and learning. By reconstructing historical recipes, and mapping out the various material and cultural contexts in which artificial stone developed, the study aims to 'follow the material', and to know history through making. In October the exhibition 'Welfare Panels' opened at Tensta konsthall in Stockholm. Produced together with colleges at KTH School of Architecture and at Catholic University of Chile, the exhibition presents the cultural, political and social framework of prefabricated concrete panel systems in the 20th century.

FIG. EXHIBITION 'WELFARE PANELS' AT TENSTA KONSTHALL
PHOTO BY JEAN-BAPTISTE BERANGER

Erik Stenberg KTH Arkitekturskolan
Helena Westerlind KTH Arkitekturskolan
Pedro Ignacio Alonso Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile
Hugo Palmarola Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile
José Hernández Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile

Välfärdsselement
Svenska miljöprogrammet byggsystem i en internationell kontext

Tensta Konsthall
2017.10.10
2018.01.14

MATERIAL GRADIENT FRP

SAMAN SAFFARIAN

ESR NUMBER: ESR12

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: STR.UCTURE, S-form

INSTITUTE: ITKE

A MATERIAL SOLUTION FOR CLIMATE ADAPTIVE ARCHITECTURAL ENVELOPES

This project investigates methods of precise fiber deployment and lay-up patterns for fabrication of Elastic Kinetic Facade Components. During the initial stages of the project, the effects of controlled geometric variations and systematic stiffness differentiations have been carefully studied in a series of prototypes with the aim of achieving higher movement efficiency, optimized cyclic performance and reduced material fatigue. The results of these experiments and investigations have been presented during the Innochain Colloquium event in Vienna in March 2017. Three pneumatically actuated elastic kinetic prototypes (FlectoFolds) were showcased in identical shape and size, but differentiated stiffness gradients. The fiber lay-up variation manifested itself in the distinctly different kinetic performance of every FlectoFold.

The knowledge acquired via prototyping and the data gathered through on-going performance tests, formed an experimental basis and a quantitative foundation that was utilized in the next stage of the project, not only to improve fiber placement and up-scaling

strategies for the materialisation of Elastic Kinetic Components, but also to tackle the shortcomings of the system in terms of digital control, resolve issues concerning the pneumatic actuation, enhance the design of supporting elements and the sub-structure, and last but not least integrate all technologies in an architecturally mature and detailed solution.

Although seemingly distant from the main focus of this project (Material Gradient FRP), these by-product investigations and design development endeavours (Integration of pneumatic actuation and electronics, Implementation of an active control interface, Design development of supporting elements and the Substructure) are crucial for successful scientific assessment of the system in research contexts, and inevitable for future implementation in construction industry.

In order to study and explore the limitations and possibilities that Elastic Kinetic Systems have brought forward, monitor their kinetic performance and associated material fatigue in long-term cycles, assess application potential on complex and free-form architectural surfaces and analyse their suitability as shading or energy harvesting systems, a large scale demonstrator (in an architecturally relevant scale), consisting of 36 FlectoFold components has been designed, detailed, fabricated, and installed as part of BauBionik Exhibition in Stuttgart (Germany) in October 2017.

In the next phase of the project, the large scale demonstrator will be used as a testing ground for monitoring, assessment and in-depth analysis of the kinetic performance of individual elements as well as the system as a whole. The collected data and gathered knowledge will inform the next steps in advancing the design, prototyping and manufacturing of Elastic Kinetic Architectural Envelopes. This project also aims to produce complimentary day-lighting and sun-shading simulations, to reinforce made assumptions, identify problems, and explore unforeseen potentials.

Applied Robotics - Controlled Material Deposition

ARTHUR PRIOR

ESR NUMBER: ESR13

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Fostert+, Buro Happold

INSTITUTE: Bartlett

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EXTENDING THE VOCABULARY OF ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

This project began in October 2015 with a simple proposition: Would it be advantageous to combine additive and subtractive manufacturing methods as part of an integrated process; In doing so, can their advantages be extracted, and their disadvantages minimised? Additive and subtractive are re-imagined here as complementary techniques, giving rise to the term 'hybrid manufacturing'. After two years of experimentation and testing, this project has converged on the development of a prototyping system for composite wax materials. Also known as industrial modelling clays, these materials have applications in industrial design (for example automotive design), where they continue to play an important role in the development and evaluation of class 'A' surfaces.

Industrial modelling clays have not been used for additive manufacturing before. Their suitability and potential for Liquid Deposition Modelling (LDM) has been investigated with a robotic test cell developed at The Bartlett Manufacturing Design

Exchange (B-MADE). This effort has been supported by Chavant, Foster+Partners and Laing O'Rourke (FreeFab) – the latter are actively pursuing hybrid technologies within the construction sector. This hybrid approach places conflicting demands on this material for performance in both additive and subtractive contexts. Studies within the past three months have aimed to characterise the rheological properties of this material. In-process measurement techniques – particularly thermal imaging – have led to new insights into the thermal dynamics that make this process possible.

What are the main benefits of this hybrid approach? Traditional additive manufacturing methods focus on the production of net-shape components. Process parameters are optimised for resolution and accuracy – layer heights in the order of 100-200µm are common, resulting in lengthy cycle times. A hybrid strategy uses additive strategies to produce near-net-shape components; material is rapidly deposited in its approximate shape with a relatively large layer height (ca. 6mm), greatly reducing cycle time. For example, the prototypes shown here were printed in a little as nine minutes. A secondary finishing operation – milling – is used to remove a small amount of material, bringing components to the final geometry. This approach combines the material efficiency and geometric freedom of additive processes with the accuracy, surface finish and speed of machining.

Who benefits from this research? Industrial modelling clays have a long history in product design, beginning in the 1920's with Harley Earl. This time-proven method, which largely depends on the dexterity and skill of sculptors, has been frequently threatened by CAD/CAM tools. In practice, however, these technologies did not have a disruptive effect, rather, they were absorbed into existing workflows as complementary tools. Today, sculpting is combined with milling, CAD surfacing tools, and 3D scanning. This research benefits the large number of industrial design studios that are committed to the use of industrial modelling clays; opening up the possibility of using this material for additive manufacturing. This research is relevant to situations where digital design methods are combined with a direct sculptural engagement with materials.

Small Scale Robotic Manufacturing for the Large Scale Building

STEPHANIE CHALTIEL

ESR NUMBER: ESR15

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: CLOUD9, ROK

INSTITUTE: IAAC

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The earthen Shells research has been published in 7 different international conferences proceedings in 2017: DMSParis (Monolithic Earthen Shells: Hybrid workflow, Kinesystem Lisbon(3d printed paste like matter), ECAADE Roma (Augmented and Virtual Reality for Monolithic earthen shells), IASS Hamburg (Monolithic shells phasing) Fab13 Santiago de Chile(Digital craft for monolithic earthen shells as housing solution), Acadia MIT Boston (Monolithic earthen shells robotic fabrication)and ASCAAD, Amman Jordan (geometric strategies for monolithic earthen shells).

This phase of extensive writing has allowed to precise the background of the technique which is at the intersection of the Bini domes from the 60's where concrete was sprayed on inflatable structures and wattle and daub principles where different layers of clay mix are applied on a light formwork following a precise phasing. It also helped narrowing down the research to drones spraying on inflatable including structure real time monitoring and phasing definition.

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While the first year of research saw the construction of many large-scale demonstrators using robotic arms where 2 different kind of traditional sprayers were connected as end effectors, the project is now entirely focused on drones spraying associated with drones 3d scanning.

Iterative recalibration of the digital tools according to constant structure monitoring is the main challenges for the next demonstrators to be built at laac's Green Lab in Barcelona. Inochain training at Smith Innovation run by Natalie Mossin has been very significant in the development of the project towards the industry and the possible market launch.

References such as Kvar cells company in Copenhagen were given with the idea of developing the earthen shells as 3d panles for interiors providing modular climatic and acoustic comfort. On the other hand, another possible industry development is to team up with agricultural drone's company such as Drones Volt and DJI but as well smaller and more recent start-ups where the technology of spraying with UAV is well developed, keeping in mind that these kinds of business may want to expand their domains of expertise.

Some specific training is being organized with Louvain university in Belgium and Obrero University in Swden to test autonomous drone flights versus flown y an expert pilot live. Autonomous flight for the first layers and flown by an expert pilot for the upper layer where the material becomes heavy on the light formwork and to prevent unplanned deformations where live action might be better. Some geometric experimentations and discovery of processing language was experimented in July 2017 with Pablo Miranda Carranza at laac Barcelona.

Some discussions with Domaine du Bois Buchet in France have taken place as the earthen shells project with drone spraying is considered for next edition of the festival in summer 2018.

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